

Studies on Some Monofluophosphates. Part II

E. B. Singh and P. C. Sinha

The infrared spectra of the hydrates of Cd, Mn, Ni, Cr(III), and Fe(III) monofluophosphates have been recorded in potassium bromide medium. Characteristic absorption bands have been observed which could be assigned to specific structural groups.

Polyatomic inorganic ions exhibit characteristic infrared spectra, which have been found useful in the analysis and identification of the compounds. Some of the studies have afforded valuable informations on the nature of the structure and of the intermolecular force. In the present investigation, absorptions of a few monofluophosphates¹ in the IR region have been recorded and attempts have been made to assign the characteristic absorption bands to the IR spectra of the monofluophosphates. No doubt we still need more empirical data before coming to a definite correlation.

EXPERIMENTAL

The IR spectra of the hydrates of monofluophosphates of cadmium, manganese, nickel, chromium, and iron were recorded in potassium bromide medium by disc technique method. The spectra are between 2 and 15 microns (Table I).

TABLE I

$\text{CdPO}_3\text{F}\cdot 8/3\text{H}_2\text{O}$.	$\text{CdPO}_3\text{F}\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$.	$\text{CdPO}_3\text{F}\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. (partially dehydrated).	$\text{MnPO}_3\text{F}\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.
3300—3400 cm^{-1} (s)	3300—3500 cm^{-1} (s)	3300—3400 cm^{-1} (s)	3250—3500 cm^{-1} (s)
2100—2200 cm^{-1} (mb)	2100—2150 cm^{-1} (vw)	1640 cm^{-1} (w)	2150 cm^{-1} (m b)
1640 cm^{-1} (s)	1640 cm^{-1} (s)	1110—1050 cm^{-1} (v b)	1640 cm^{-1} (v s)
1125—1130 cm^{-1} (vs b)	1150 cm^{-1} (s)	720 cm^{-1} (w)	1125—1170 cm^{-1} (s b)
1040 cm^{-1} (m)	1080 cm^{-1} (s)		1020 cm^{-1} (v s)
830 cm^{-1} (s)	1010—1020 cm^{-1} (s)		825—830 cm^{-1} (s)
760 cm^{-1} (s b)	830 cm^{-1} (s)		750—760 (w b)
$\text{NiPO}_3\text{F}\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$.	$\text{Cr}_2(\text{PO}_3\text{F})_3\cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$.	$\text{Fe}_2(\text{PO}_3\text{F})_3\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.	$\text{CdSO}_4\cdot 8/3\text{H}_2\text{O}$.
3450 cm^{-1} (w)	3340 cm^{-1} (v s)	3350 cm^{-1} (s)	3500—3400 cm^{-1} (s)
1640 cm^{-1} (w)	1640 cm^{-1} (v s)	2300—2400 cm^{-1} (vw)	1640 cm^{-1} (s)
1140 cm^{-1} (w)	1140 cm^{-1} (s b)	1640 cm^{-1} (s)	1110 cm^{-1} (s b)
1125 cm^{-1} (w)	1055 cm^{-1} (m)	1050—1140 cm^{-1} (v b sh)	
1025 cm^{-1} (w)	830—860 cm^{-1} (s b sh)	730 cm^{-1} (v b)	
830 cm^{-1} (b)			

vw = very weak. w = weak. m = medium. s = strong. vs = very strong. sh = shoulder. b = Broad vb = very broad.

1. Singh and Sinha, this issue, p. 407.

DISCUSSION

The positions and the intensities of the IR bands of the compounds, recorded in Table I, show reasonable similarities among themselves. Monofluorophosphates, which possess the same structural group,

are found to have absorption bands of the same general shape and relative intensities at slightly different wave lengths. By comparing such spectra, it could be possible to assign some of these bands to specific structural group.

All these bands are in agreement with the IR spectra of some monofluorophosphates, recorded by Corbridge and Low², Pustinger *et al.*³, and by Kihl⁴. The characteristic absorption bands may be assigned to different structural linkages in the monofluorophosphate hydrate and are due to the following stretching vibrations: (1) P=O, (2) P—F, (3) H—O—H.

P=O Vibrations.—The phosphate ion has been reported, on the basis of the Raman spectra⁵, to absorb at 1082cm⁻¹ and 980cm⁻¹. In infrared studies, the latter band normally does not appear. Colthup⁶ recorded for phosphate ion a band at 1100-1040 cm⁻¹. Miller and Wilkins⁷ in examining a few orthophosphates observed a strong broad band at 1030cm⁻¹ to 1000 cm⁻¹. Bellamy and Beccher⁸⁻⁹ also observed absorption in this region. Corbridge and Low² found strong absorption between 1150 and 1000 cm⁻¹. In some cases a single band is found and in others strong absorption often consisting of multiplet peaks occur over the range 1170-1000 cm⁻¹ and is connected with P=O stretching. Other workers¹⁰⁻¹⁶ from the study of organo-phosphorus compounds, consisting of phosphorus—oxygen linkages, also obtained the above results.

In the monofluorophosphates, the anion containing P—O linkage absorbs in the same region. One oxygen atom of the trivalent tetrahedral orthophosphate ion has been substituted with a fluorine atom, making the anion divalent. The substitution has caused a little shift in the wave length of IR absorption of the phosphoryl vibration, because variation in the wave length depends on the nature of the substituent group or atom.

2. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 4555.
3. *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1959, **11**, 909.
4. *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1662, 1466.
5. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 423.
6. *J. Opt. Soc. Amer.*, 1950, **40**, 307.
7. *Anal. Chem.* 1952, **24**, 1253.
8. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 728.
9. *Ibid.*, 1952, 475, 1701.
10. Meyrie and Thompson, *ibid.*, 1950, 225.
11. Gore, *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1950, **9**, 138.
12. Daasch and Smith, *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, **23**, 853.
13. Bergmann *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 847
14. Erich, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 621.
15. Bell *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1954, **76**, 5196.
16. Daasch and Smith, *ibid.*, 1954, **76**, 3403.

Corbridge and Low¹⁷ connected the difference between position of the ionic phosphate absorption bands of the monofluophosphates and of methyl phosphonate with the large difference in electro-negative character of the attached fluorine and methyl group.

P—F Vibrations.—The absorptions at 830-720 cm^{-1} found in all the monofluophosphates are probably due to P—F stretching. The regions for PF_3 , POF_3 and PF_5 ^{17,18} have been found to be between 990 and 840 cm^{-1} and the absorption between 830 and 720 cm^{-1} has now been generally accepted to be the characteristic for all monofluophosphates.

H—O—H Vibrations.—All hydrated salts absorb in the 3300 cm^{-1} and 1640 cm^{-1} regions, which presumably correspond to O—H stretching and O—H bonding respectively. Buswell and Dulongbostel¹⁹ have established that 2.75 microns (3300 cm^{-1}) band represents unbounded OH and when hydrogen bonding occurs, there is a shift to longer wave length (3 microns). It has been found that on dehydration these bands are fully or partially eliminated and the overall spectrum is considerably altered; some new bands appear, some are suppressed, or eliminated, or shifted towards shorter wave length. The introduction of water molecules into the lattice usually results in rearrangement of the packing and adoption of a different crystalline form; the water molecule may form hydrogen bonding with some part of the anion and consequently affects their vibrational frequencies.

Mixed Crystals.—The sulphate ion, which is analogous to the monofluophosphate ion, does not exhibit the same kind of spectra. The spectrum of the mixed crystals of monofluophosphate and the corresponding sulphate is observed to be essentially the sum of the spectra of the individual components with little shift and alteration in the positions and the intensities of absorptions. The regions of the absorption of the ionic phosphate and sulphate are so close that in the mixed crystals of sulphate and monofluophosphate, the absorption bands of both combine to form a very broad absorption band round about 1100 cm^{-1} . In the double salt with ammonium monofluophosphate, an extra band for ammonium radical appears at 3200-3100 cm^{-1} and the second at 1430-1390 cm^{-1} . The rest of the bands are usual (Table II),

TABLE II

$\text{CaPO}_3\text{F} \cdot \text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 8/3 \text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{MnPO}_3\text{F} \cdot \text{MnSO}_4 \cdot 4 \text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{NiPO}_3\text{F} \cdot \text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7 \text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{Cr}_2(\text{PO}_3\text{F})_3 \cdot 3(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{PO}_3\text{F}$
3400 cm^{-1} (s)	3350—3300 cm^{-1} (s)	3350 cm^{-1} (s)	3200—3100 cm^{-1} (s)
1640 cm^{-1} (s)	2200—2100 cm^{-1} (w b)	2300 cm^{-1} (vw)	1640 cm^{-1} (vw)
1110 cm^{-1} (s, b)	1500 cm^{-1} (m)	1640 cm^{-1} (s)	1430—1390 cm^{-1} (s)
720 cm^{-1} (w)	1090—1100 cm^{-1} (s b)	1375 cm^{-1} (vw)	1170—1020 cm^{-1} (v b)
	1015 cm^{-1} (m)	1080—1100 cm^{-1} (s b)	900 cm^{-1} (vw)
	820 cm^{-1} (b)	920 cm^{-1} (w)	820 cm^{-1} (vw)
		840 cm^{-1} (w b)	740 cm^{-1} (vw)
		750 cm^{-1} (w b)	

The positions and intensities of IR bands of the above monofluophosphates have been found slightly different in each case and it might have been affected by crystal structure environments, the nature of the positive ions, hydrogen-bonded water, and

17. Gorrard, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 1454.

18. Delwaille and Francois, *Compt. rend.*, 1947, 224, 1422.

19. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 2554.

interaction with lattice frequencies. Reasons may be advanced as to why a frequency may shift slightly as the positive ion is changed. The different charges, mass, and the radii of the various positive ions produce different electrical fields in the various salts. These doubtless affect the vibrational frequencies of the negative PO_3F^{2-} ion. Changing the positive ion may produce a different crystalline arrangement resulting in a different symmetry or intensity of the electrical field around the negative ion. A difference in the type or extent of hydration also alters some of the frequencies as described earlier. Miller and Wilkins⁷ recorded and compared IR spectra of ten sulphates and observed considerable variation between the individual sulphates.

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CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
PATNA UNIVERSITY,
PATNA-5.

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